

Marketing Strategy Performance for Decision Making In Choosing the Head of Regional Community

(A Survey on the Election of Governor of North Sumatera Province, Indonesia)

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Introduction

Indonesia is a country that has the largest population in the world - after Tiongkok, India, and United States - has great potential to carry out a good democracy in the election of leaders, including the President and the Head of the Region, namely the governor and regent.

Direct general election in according to the the mandate of the law that have been issued by the government provides that the implementation of the governors election, regent and mayor to make prospective candidates who will advance in the election trying to give an appointment to convince people to vote in the candidate winning effort. To be able to convince the audience of voters the candidates to make efforts in the political appointments to the society as marketing targets that will be collected as supplier of winning voice.

According Tjiptono and Chandra (2012: 24) that marketing target is the transition of an effort to sell to each person to be the best serve target markets specifically formulated according to the market needed. Market target in vote community decision is the most fundamental thing in winning the election directly. Imaging through a work program or imaging a person in attempt to increase the bargaining power or influence to give a vote decision to the regional head candidates.

Demographically North Sumatra province is the fourth largest region after the West Java Province, East Java, and Central Java. The number of population and number of communities that have been able to give their voting is 10.227.586 voters by updating the data in 2014 from the central KPU. With an area 72:981.23 km² the number of regent and cities 33 regions so the regional elections of North Sumatra province the contestants who participated in the general elections of Regent requires special attention to be able to win the competition in the elections.

North Sumatra has potential in local elections relatively with community enthusiasm. In fact their enthusiasm to vote at the local elections in North Sumatra relatively low. Based of the data obtained from several districts in North Sumatra, the average voter who attended to TPS is not up to 70 percent, some even less than 3/4 of the existing DPT.

Regional Head of North Sumatera province in the implementation of the direct election system is a recent phenomenon as development of marketing management science. The effect of local elections can open up opportunities for the creation of political marketing to the local government and become new economic development. The form of direct elections of head regent is implemented because has the spirit by Presiden direct election to give. (Interview of Djohermansyah Djohan, Director General of Regional Autonomy, Reuters, 14/04/11).

According Wesesa, (2013: xxxi) Applications political marketing science push a lot of thought into political practices, especially for the electoral process, legislative and regional political marketing practices. In head general election that political work program is part of the product that is offered by contestants it is dictated by Pawitra, (2005: 8) that the marketing focus is not limited to relational relations but also on networking as the reality of today's business, for example on social relations.

The decision to choose the head of the local communities in North Sumatra relatif low. This was confirmed also by the initial survey (2014) in 50 voters scattered on district / city in North Sumatra, the indicators put forth by Benjamin and Shapiro (2007: 5) states that the indicator regional head candidate who is predicted to win the competition is high elektability.

Formulation Problems

1. How does the performance of the market strategy, marketing mix strategies, and the decision of the people in choosing a candidate in the local elections of North Sumatra province.
2. The extent to which the performance of the market strategy and marketing mix strategies candidate against the decision of the community, either partially or simultaneously

Literature Riview

Political Marketing

Lynch (2009) had proposed the idea, citing Baines et al (2001) that in history, marketing in politics has ideas knowledge of marketing, concepts, and frameworks in studies of consumption goods and services. It is no wonder then O'Leary et al (1976) in Niffenegger (1989) states that the basis used in the context of political marketing refer to the product orientation in marketing mix. Recently Baines et al (2001) found a marketing study can grounding more useful in analyzing political marketing activities, and can also be applied in marketing strategy, certainly in the context of politics.

Additionally, Baines (2002) asserts that in scholarly, political marketing is a study that is still new and still in emryonic area. Although relatively new discipline of science, (Shama, 1975; Lock and harris, 1996, in Wrings 1997) identifies that political marketing is actually a process of communication between voters with the party and its candidates regardless of organizational components.

Within the framework of goods or services of consumption, marketing strategies politics focuses on a few things in the study disciplines marketing strategies such as segmentation (Bradshaw, 1995), positioning (Butler and Collins, 1994, in Baines et al, 1999), the development of the message (Baer, 1995), campaign management (Newman, 1994), as well as market orientation (O'Cass, 1996).

Market Strategy Performance

Market strategy is a market selection strategy based on the specific orientation of the company to customers in offering goods or services by defining the wishes of customers (Zeithaml & Bitner, 2000: 103).

With the target market strategy in the post-purchase phase of a product offered by the company, will eventually also affect the standard of service provided by the company. Customers in evaluating a product that will shape demand, typically will be used as a base or standard of quality of service that will be delivered by the company to the customer. The magnitude of the difference between the demands of the reality will depend on the perception of the customer

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2008: 245) relating to the product positioning plan of putting something in the minds of consumers who become target. Positioning market this product has also been alluded to Kotler and Kotler (1999) in one of the stages of marketing activities related to political marketing as environmental research. The research to environment is a first step that must be done to prepare for the marketing map candidate (candidate marketing map) which consists of a thorough analysis of the social environment in which the campaign will be carried out. This study (environmental research) focuses on exploring opportunities with intimidations will be faced. Environment in this case include the condition of economic each country, social issues, economic and politic or anything else provoke voter emotion. How the political expert describe / saw the candidate / party, orientation, ideology as for as domination of the party on (Kotler and Kotler, 1999). The region with demography condition and psycografy from the voter.

Marketing Mix Strategy Performance

Based on Kotler and Keller (2014: 63) the marketing mix is a set of marketing tools in which companies use to achieve marketing goals in target market. In market preparation of the marketing mix strategy there are a

number of factors to be considered include the criteria for performance management, corporate resources, corporate strategy, market objectives and strategies of competitors.

Source: Kotler and Keller (2014: 16)

Figure 2.1
Marketing Mix Strategy

McCarthy (Kotler & Keller, 2014: 63) classifies the marketing tools into four groups called the four Ps of marketing: product, price, place and promotion. As for services, the 3P plus, namely people, physical evidence, and process.

According to Kotler and Keller (2014: 369) the product mix of a company has four important dimensions are: width (number of product lines), length (number of items of the product line), depth (number of versions of each product offered) and consistency (consistency of product the target market, production, distribution and others). The four dimensions of the product to be hold in the preparation of the product mix strategy.

In this study, the mix of this process is an attempt candidates in the running and carrying out activities to meet the needs and desires of the community. The process involves procedures, tasks, schedules, mechanisms, activities and routines with what the work program / policy offered distributed to the public.

Decision

Research has shown that people's behavior is difficult to predict, even for experts in their study. Marketing, is an asset that influence people's behavior analysis as an interest to invest, which is composed of awarnest, interest, desire, and action. In this respect the community's decision to invest in the candidates head of certain areas is an asset for candidates Regional Head to know the behavior of people who are focused on interest to invest, so that the cost of the campaign can be overcome, but the consequences are if elected must pay attention to the people concerned, this is the political sphere, Silayoi and Speece (2004: 610) states that the consumer decision-making can be defined as a mental orientation that characterizes the approach of consumers to make choices.

The definition indicates that in making the selection decision, the public will have a particular approaches individually and separately before deciding to choose institution on one candidate or several kandidat. society decision is a mental orientation that characterizes the community approach to make a choice. Dimention of community decisions are based on the work program of the candidate, candidate elektability,

the track record of the candidate, the popularity of the candidate, the candidate as a native son, and political party machine that carries candidates.

Figure 2.2
Research Paradigm

Research Methods

The method used in this research is descriptive explanatory, with the aim to obtain a description of the market strategy performance, marketing mix strategy performance, the value of community and community decisions, and determine the relationship between variables by testing the hypothesis of the results of data collection in the field. In addition, this approach requires direct interaction between the researcher and the researched, as well as expert resource persons / experts to gain a holistic understanding and depth. Furthermore, the generalization is based on the results of tests on samples.

Based on one of the goals of this research is to measure the degree of influence of the independent variable (market strategy performance and general performance of marketing mix strategy) on the dependent variable (the value of community and community decisions), it is a tool of analysis in this research is to use Structural Equation Model (SEM).

Sources of Data and Method Determination of Data / Information

This research is the perception of research subjects, which in this case are the voters on Election North Sumatra province, therefore the type of data in this research is the data subject (self-report data), so that the data were obtained directly from the source, namely the voters Pemilukada province of North Sumatra. While the source of the data, namely (1) Secondary data sources are from a variety of sources, including journals, reports the Regional Commission, magazines, etc., that includes aspects in fulfilling the needs of research. (2) Sources of primary data that voters on Election province of North Sumatra. (3) The primary data source that is considered an expert / on Election North Sumatera Province.

The population in this study is voters in the North Sumatra Provincial Election in 2013 which amounted to 10,310,872 voters. Determining the number of samples in this study by using proportional random sampling

technique, the sample size calculation using the formula Slovin voters. From the calculation of the sample, obtained minimum voters sample of 400 voters.

For the determination of the next sample to determine expert opinion use sampling techniques non-probability sampling with a specific purpose in accordance with the interests of the study is to obtain data that accurately and deeply studied in with not too long time. Responden in this study for the in-depth interview is Chairman KPU of North Sumatra in terms of practitioners, to terms of academics are Dr. Edi, and from the standpoint of public figures is Jumiran Abdi.

Data Collection Techniques

This research is the perception of the object of research, which in this case are the voters on Election North Sumatra province, therefore the type of data in this research is the data subject (self-report data), so that the data were obtained directly from the source, namely (data primary) and secondary data necessary for support data. Data of two types of data collected with the technique as follows:

1. Interview

Interviews were conducted with some of the voters registered in the DPT North Sumatra province, spread in regencies / cities to obtain the necessary data, both primary and secondary in the observation unit. Interviews were also conducted to locate and verify the phenomenon gained from observation.

2. Questionnaire

A questionnaire was used as a measuring tool for collecting primary data from all the people (voters) Election in North Sumatera province. Determines whether the respondents had difficulty in understanding all the questions and in answering questions, the first conducted a pretest.

3. Observation

Observation, make observations directly to obtain other information that cannot be predicted in advance or are not included in the questionnaire, analyzing and reviewing records / annual reports, other documents from various institutions in connection with the problems to be studied.

Analysis of Verification

In the verification study used quantitative analysis using structural equation modeling (Structural Equation Modeling / SEM) based variants or components, PLS (Partial Least Square) to verify the relationship between variables. Selection of PLS analysis method in this study is based on suitability criteria of the research and analysis necessary prerequisite. Data analysis and structural equation modeling using PLS carried out as follows:

1. Designing structural models (inner model)

Inner Model describes relationship between latent variables based on substantive theory. The design of the structural model based on the formulation of the problem or the research hypothesis.

2. Designing a measurement model (outer model)

Outer Model defines how each block indicator associated with latent variables. The design of this measurement model to determine the nature of each indicator latent variables.

3. Construction Line Diagram

Path diagram illustrates the relationship between the variables and indicators of latent and dimensions of the structural equation modeling with PLS. Referring to the operationalization of variables where measurement

of latent variables is done through a dimension, then the path diagram used in this study is the Second Order Partial Least Square.

4. Conversion into the path diagram of the system of equations

- a. Inner Model (Structural Model). Construction of the model equations in Figure 3.1, can be derived equations for the inner workings of the model as follows:

$$\eta_1 = \gamma_1\xi_1 + \gamma_2\xi_2 + \zeta_1$$

$$\eta_2 = \gamma_1\xi_1 + \gamma_2\xi_2 + \beta_1\eta_1 + \zeta_2$$

- b. Outer Model (Model Measurement). A specification of the relationship between latent variables with indicators that define the characteristics of the construct with its manifest variables.

5. Parameter Estimation

Parameter estimation method (estimated) in PLS is the least squares method (least square methods). The calculation process is done by iteration, where iteration will stop if it has reached convergent condition.

6. Suitability Evaluation Model

Suitability evaluation model in PLS is done by testing the measurement model (outer model) as well as the structural model (inner model).

Test on the measurement model (outer model) conducted to examine the relationship between latent variables with the indicator, among others: Convergent Validity, Discriminant Validity, Construct Reliability, Cronbach Alpha.

While testing the structural models (inner model) conducted to examine the relationship between latent variables, namely the feasibility of the model and the significance of its tracks, among others: R Square (R²), Estimated for Path Coefficient, Effect Size (f²), Relevanced Prediction (Q²), Goodness of Fit (GoF).

7. Interpretation and Modification Model

Models are built next is to interpret and modify according to the evaluation of the suitability of the model.

Discussion

Hypothesis Verification

To test the hypothesis of the study, used methods Partial Least Square (PLS) with a second order for the measurement of each construct the indicator variable is done through the dimensions as shown in the model in Chapter 3. Hypothesis test research involved 400 respondents and to facilitate the calculation of researchers using statistical software XLSTAT 2014.

Model Market Strategy Performance:

Market strategy performance variables are measured using two-dimensional there are target market strategy performance (X1.1) and the performance of the market positioning strategy (X1.2). Each dimensions are measured by several indicators that this measurement models using model second order. Base on model second of the data processing using XLSTAT 2014 obtained the measurement results as shown in Table 4.22 below.

Table 4.27

Performance Measurement Model calculation Variable Market Strategy

Dimension	Simbol	Standardized Loadings	R ²	Varians Error	t-test	Specification
Target market strategy performance	X1.1	0.868	0.753	0.247	34.926	Valid
Performance of market positioning strategy	X1.2	0.871	0.758	0.242	35.316	Valid
Composite Reliability (CR) = 0.842						
Average Variance Extracted (AVE) = 0.517						
Cronbach's alpha= 0.764						

Model Marketing Mix Performance:

Variable marketing mix performance was measured using seven dimensions of product mix politics (X2.1), the mix price in the marketing politics (X2.2), distribution mix (X2.3), the promotion mix (X2.4), mix HR (X2.5), a mix of physical evidence (X2.6) and mix process (X2.7). Each dimension is measured by several indicators that this measurement models using model second order. Base on model second of the data processing using XLSTAT 2014 obtained by the measurement results as shown in Table 4.30 below.

Table 4.3
Performance Measurement Model calculation Variable Marketing Mix

Dimension	Simbol	Standardized Loadings	R ²	Varians Error	t-test	Specification
Politic product mix	X2.1	0.693	0.480	0.520	19.158	Valid
Price mix in political mix	X2.2	0.569	0.323	0.677	13.787	Valid
Distribution mix	X2.3	0.775	0.600	0.400	24.459	Valid
Promotion mix	X2.4	0.705	0.497	0.503	19.843	Valid
HR mix	X2.5	0.505	0.255	0.745	11.677	Valid
Physical evidence mix	X2.6	0.755	0.570	0.430	22.965	Valid
Process mix	X2.7	0.711	0.505	0.495	20.161	Valid
Composite Reliability (CR) = 0.901						
Average Variance Extracted (AVE) = 0.318						
Cronbach's alpha= 0.884						

Decision Model Society:

Community decision variables are measured using the six dimensions of the work program candidates (Y2.1), elektibilitas candidate (Y2.2), the track record of the candidate (Y2.3), the popularity of the candidate (Y2.4), candidates as native son (Y2.5) and political party machine (Y2.6). Each dimension is measured by several indicators that this measurement models using order. Berdasarkan second model of the data processing using XLSTAT 2014 obtained by the measurement results as shown in Table 4.41 below.

Table 4.41
The decision variable calculation Measurement Model Society

Dimention	Simbol	Standardized Loadings	R ²	Varians Error	t-test	Specification
Candidate work program	Y2.1	0.820	0.673	0.327	28.612	Valid
Candidate Electability	Y2.2	0.731	0.534	0.466	21.377	Valid
Candidate track record	Y2.3	0.847	0.717	0.283	31.788	Valid
Candidate Popularity	Y2.4	0.760	0.578	0.422	23.340	Valid
Candidate as a sons of soil	Y2.5	0.817	0.668	0.332	28.289	Valid
Political Party Machine	Y2.6	0.731	0.534	0.466	21.345	Valid
Composite Reliability (CR) = 0.928						
Average Variance Extracted (AVE) = 0.500						
Cronbach's alpha = 0.916						

Effect of Market Strategy Performance and Marketing Mix Performance to Public Decision Either Partially or Simultaneous.

The calculation result of the path diagram the second hypothesis (H3) that influences the performance of a market strategy and marketing mix performance against the decision of the people either partially or simultaneously shown in Figure 4.6 below.

To test this hypothesis H3 testing the hypothesis as follows:

Simultaneous Hypothesis:

H0: There is no performance effect of market strategy and performance of the marketing mix to society decision either simultaneously or partially;

Ha: There is the influence of the performance of the market strategy and performance of the marketing mix to society decision either simultaneously or partially.

To test the hypothesis of simultaneous use statistical tests F with the results as shown in Table 4.55 below.

Table 4:55
Simultaneous Hypothesis Testing Results (H3)

Hypothesis	R ²	F	F-table	Decission
There is the influence of market strategy performance and marketing mix performance affect to public decission simultaneously or partially	0.719	337.356	3.018	Significant (H ₀ refused)

Based on the results of hypothesis testing simultaneous above, the value of the F-count (337 356) is greater than the value of the F-table is 3018 which indicates that the H0 is refused so that it can be concluded that there are significant performance market strategy and performance of the marketing mix to society decision either simultaneously or partially.

Partial Hypothesis 3a:

Influence Performance Market Strategy to Decision Society

H0: There is no performance effect on the decision public market strategies;

Ha: There is the influence of the performance of the market strategy of the public decision.

H3a partial hypothesis testing results are shown in the table below.

Table 4.56
Influence Market Strategy Performance to Public Decision

Variable	Coefficient Effect	T-count	T-table ($\alpha = 5\%$)	Conclusion
Market strategy performace	0.004	0.111	1.966	Not Significant (H ₀ accepted)
Direct impact coeffisient		0.004		Effect Total Coeffisient
Indirect impact coeffisient		0		0.004

According to the table above, it can be seen that the market strategy performance is not significantly influence public decisions, where the value t count obtained is smaller than t-table is $0.111 < 1.966$ (H₀). The influence of market strategy performance of the community is a positive decision by influence coefficient of 0.004 or market strategy performance has a direct impact of 0.001% ($0.004 \times 0.004 \times 100\%$).

Partial Hypothesis 3b:

The Effect of Marketing Mix Performance to Public Decision

H0: There is no effect of the marketing mix performance to public decision;

Ha: There is the influence of the marketing mix performance to public decision.

H3b partial hypothesis testing results are shown in the table below.

Table 4.57
Effect of Marketing Mix Performance to Public Decision

Variable	Coefficient Effect	T-count	T-table ($\alpha = 5\%$)	Conclusion
Marketing mix performance	0.282	6.506	1.966	Significant (H ₀ refused)
Direct impact coeffisient		0.282		Total coefficient effect
Indirect impact coefficient effect		0		0.282

According to the table 4.57 above, it can be seen that the performance of the marketing mix significantly influence public decisions, where the value t count that is greater than the value of the t-table is $6.506 > 1.966$ (H₀ refused). Influence the marketing mix performance to the community is a positive decision by influence coefficient of 0.282 or the performance of the marketing mix has a direct impact of 7.96% ($0.282 \times 0.282 \times 100\%$).

Discussion of Variable Performance Market Strategy

Based on the value of standardized loading factor in Figure 4.2 and Table 4:27 shows that both dimensions inferred valid because the t-count value of each dimension is greater than 1.96 with a composite reliability greater than 0.7 or $0.842 > 0.70$ and Cronbach's alpha values amounting to 0.764. Measure the dimensions of the most dominant variable "performance market strategy" is the dimension of "performance market positioning strategy".

According to Kotler and Kotler (1999), the dimensions of "performance market positioning strategy" can determine the variable "performance market strategy" because contact with the social environment in which the campaign will be held. Environment in this case include the economic conditions of a region, social issues, politics, or anything that may provoke voters and psychographics of voters.

According to the Abdi Jumiran in this study as an opponent of experts from among the community leaders who are concerned on politics and the election, a phenomenon that occurs in the discussion of the performance variable market strategy is described as follows:

"... As long as it is usually the candidate's campaign was so like all kinds. There are suddenly speaking local languages but rigid. But the accent like that makes many people feel entertained, and easy to remember. "

As for the dimension "performance target market strategy" does not dominate, or do not specify variable "performance market strategy". This phenomenon got the attention of Dr. Edi in this study as a resource opponent experts from academia were found

"... Something that could appear physically from political parties and candidates that could give certain impressions to the public. Of course things like this kind of meaningless political penting. Marketing until this point they have in common with the marketing of the product or jasa. Tapi, if passed, a different concept in its implementation when political parties and candidates for regional leaders who carried describes the vision, mission and work program. However, if viewed from the conditions now, people are not so concerned with the work program carried by leaders in the election"

Discussion of Variable Performance Marketing Mix

Based on the value of standardized loading factor in Figure 4.3 and Table 4:30 shows that the seven dimensions of inferred valid because the t-count value of each dimension is greater than 1.96 with a composite reliability greater than 0.7 or $0.901 > 0.70$ and Cronbach's alpha values amounting to 0.884. Dimensions of the most dominant variables to measure the performance of the marketing mix is the dimension of distribution mix.

In the proposed marketing mix Kotler and Keller (2014: 63) is one of a set of marketing tools that companies use to achieve marketing goals in the target market. The stage in choosing a distribution strategy, according to Cravens and Piercy (2003: 345-346) consists of determination of the type of distribution, intensity distribution, and selection of distribution configurations. In this study, the distribution mix the institutions or organizations involved in the winning candidate in elections, such as survey organizations, political parties, a successful team, media, and so forth, so that people know what will be offered by the candidate.

North Sumatra provincial KPU chairman stated that there are various attempts candidate in activities aimed at meeting the needs of society.

"It can be seen in areas of party activity, increasingly, when approaching Regional Election. The observation reports received, the party cadres have started to communicate and begin to introduce candidates for regional leaders who proposed. It can be seen also from the newspapers how the model has begun leaning issues here and there, you know. But it's a nice, dynamic democracy. People are starting mapped through surveys, is a little more to help us"

While the lowest dimensions in determining the variable performance of the marketing mix is the dimension mix HR. Boyatzis, (2008: 8) argues that the definition of human resources competencies are behaviors that manifest one's talents. While SHRM, (2011: 1) argue that competencies are "knowledge, skills, abilities, and other qualities". Competence is the knowledge, skills, abilities, and other qualities possessed by individuals. However McEvoy et al., (2005) has another opinion, that an HRM professional competence is "in what a person knows, and does that is causally related to superior performance as an HR professional". HR professional competence is what someone know and do the causes of their superior performance as a human resources professional. Based on the above statement, Regional Head candidates' competency is what the

candidates know about the need to implement the promises offered, so that they are perceived by the public will generate good performance as Head of Region.

Dr. Edi expressed about the phenomenon that occurs in the human resources mix dimensions as follows. "Each candidate during the campaign was always promising and intends to develop areas for the welfare of society ... prosperous the society and building area at the time is no longer a top down. No the public should have participated. In this condition if we talked about people's participations, all of the regional leader candidate must know, understanding and understand the culture of the people. We cannot suddenly come and urged the people to do this and that, we might call it contrary to the habits of the local community, right."

Discussion of Public Decision Variable

Finding public decision based on USA election (2007:41). The election winning indicator is a track record from the candidate. Reid (1988) adapted the concept of buyer decision process to politic world become voting decision process. One of the stage in voting decision process is the outcome where the politician maximalize voters satisfaction (his voter or not) which implemented the programme offered in the campaign. One of dimension from public decision is track record. In this phenomenon Dr. Edi has argued as follow:

" People has opportunity to see the history together from the action of political party in their region as judgment in choosing their regional leader. The existence of mass media which explored their candidate continuously is used by public as a judgment to choose".

Conclusion

Market strategy performance partially is not significant influence to public decision. Concerning this case, the expert give attention that although a candidate provoke public attention successfully with know and understand regional culture. However in making decision, public judge the biography's candidate which can be accessed from the news.

Marketing mix partially significant influence to public decision. Market strategy performance to public decision. Market strategy performance and marketing mix performance influence simultaneously to public decision.

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